

Optimization of the Flexible Manufacturing Systems by Using the Shannon Entropy and EDAS Method

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Abstract: Most manufacturing companies aim to improve their production methods to obtain a competitive edge as global rivalry grows. Among these manufacturing technologies are flexible manufacturing systems. Systems for flexible production can create a wide range of goods in predetermined quantities with short lead times. Production organizations have started utilizing flexible production systems to profit from the growing use of modern technologies. Numerous contradictory factors need to be considered while assessing or choosing flexible production systems, numerous contradictory factors must be considered. Therefore, flexible manufacturing systems are either selected or evaluated using the MCDM method. So in this study, we will use the EDAS technique based on entropy to identify flexible manufacturing systems. The entropy approach will be used to calculate the objective criterion weights and rank the alternatives using the EDAS method. This approach ranks eight distinct alternatives based on their respective performances.

Keywords: Multi-criteria Decision Making (MCDM), EDAS Method, Flexible Manufacturing Systems, Shannon's Entropy Method.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the present time, due to increasing global competition, manufacturing companies need advanced production technologies such as computer-controlled machines, automatic material handling systems, and FMS to quickly meet customer needs and gain a competitive advantage in the global market. With the spread of advanced technology, FMS has attracted the attention of many manufacturing companies and many companies have switched to this system. An FMS is composed of machine tools and/or robots linked by a transport network and controlled by a central computer to move parts and/or tools [17]. The term "flexible" refers to the system's ability to process different types of parts simultaneously at various workstations, with the capability to easily adjust the mix of part types and production quantities in response to changing demand, as noted by Chatterjee and Chakraborty [5]. Potential benefits of using FMS include reducing stock levels, reducing production lead time, reducing installation costs, and providing high flexibility and quality [17].

FMSs are systems that can produce various products in the desired quantity in a short time. Therefore, having FMS has become a necessity for many manufacturers. In addition, since the installation of FMS requires a large investment, the selection of the most suitable FMS requires comprehensive analysis and evaluation by Chatterjee and Chakraborty [5]. Therefore, to get the most benefit from the system in the selection of FMS, a detailed criteria scan must be made and the importance of these criteria must be determined correctly. If some of these criteria conflict with each other, measurement becomes difficult and a balance must be established between these criteria when the preferences of the decision-makers in the production enterprise are taken into account of Chatterjee and Chakraborty [5]. Since many criteria are included in the selection phase of FMS, the MCDM method has been used many times in the literature on FMS selection.

Some of the MCDM methods used for FMS selection in the literature are as follows; AHP by Chan et al. [4]; and Bayazit [2], consensus rating method by Rao [23], TOPSIS by Karsak

[17] and axiomatic design method by Kulak and Kahraman [19]. One of the studies conducted for FMS evaluation and selection in recent years is the study of Chatterjee and Chakraborty [5], in which more than one multi-criterion decision-making method was used together for FMS selection. The authors used the Entropy method to determine the criterion weights and used what they call preference ranking methods (EVAMIX, COPRAS, ORESTE, OCRA, and EDAS) in ranking the FMSs. In another study, Talebanpour and Javadi [29] evaluated the decisions of whether or not to install EUS by using the DEMATEL method. The DEMATEL method was used to find the relationship density between the criteria and calculate the weight of the criteria. The DEMATEL method evaluated decisions about whether or not to install FMS. Ervural et al. [13] evaluated flexible production systems by combining heuristic fuzzy logic and multi-attribute group decision-making methods in another study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The discipline of production management is relevant to this study. Kabir and Suzuki [16] state that the core components of field material handling systems include computer numerical control machine tools, which are loaded and unloaded, along with automated material handling devices by advanced industrial robots, computer-controlled storage and retrieval systems, and other automated equipment. According to Demesure et al. [6], FMS issues are divided into four categories: design, planning, scheduling, and control. The right amount of each type of machine tool, the capacity handling system of the material, and the buffer size are among the design issues with FMSs. Planning issues in FMSs include choosing which parts to process at the same time, grouping machine tools optimally, assigning operations to different components, and assigning pallets and fixtures to different part types. Finding the ideal order for machine tools and components as input sequences is one of the scheduling issues associated with FMSs. Monitoring the system to make sure that requirements and deadlines are followed and that unreliability issues are taken into account are known as FMS control problems by Priore et al. [22]; Demesure et al. [6]; Lee et al. [20]; and Souier et al. [27]. The design challenge is

the main topic of the study that is being suggested in this paper.

Prior research has concentrated on machine flexibility and routing, which affect several performance metrics. Productivity enhancement, machine selection, number allotted, capacity, buffer sizes, pallet allocations, material handling systems, jigs and fixtures allocations, FMS planning, scheduling, optimization of limited resources, and FMS controls are among the issues associated with FMSs by Lee et al. [20]; and Bi et al. [3]. Ram et al. [36] validated the ranks obtained from TOPSIS and T-GRA.

Based on the aforementioned investigations, researchers have identified several elements that have a major influence on the performance of FMSs. The writers include a variety of topics, including the need for design modifications in the final product, cutting circumstances, worker skill and adaptability, sequencing flexibility, routing flexibility, part sequencing, and figuring out the maximum number of routes. MCDM techniques, such as Fuzzy MICMAC or ISM, have been used in several studies to assess the impact of compelling factors and variables on the performance of flexible manufacturing systems. Furthermore, to find the ideal value of variables and improve the overall performance of flexible manufacturing systems, further research has concentrated on optimization or simulation-based optimization techniques. The DoE and statistical analysis have been the main tools utilized by other researchers to evaluate the impact of various variables and factors on FMS performance. By using a hybrid framework that combines MCDM, Entropy, and EDAS simulation, the suggested framework achieves all of these goals. The stated goals and possible capabilities are demonstrated by applying this technique to an actual industrial situation.

This study employs the entropy and EDAS method for selecting an FMS. Its originality lies in the fact that the entropy and EDAS methods have not previously been applied to FMS selection. Given that the decision matrix was already known, the Entropy method was utilized to determine the objective weights. The CRITIC method, which is another method of

finding objective weights, was not preferred in this study because it requires more processing. In MCDMs such as PROMETHEE and ELECTRE, increasing the number of alternatives increases the processing time. Even though the number of alternatives increases in the ROV method, the processing time is very short compared to these methods since pairwise comparison is not made. Therefore, the EDAS method was preferred in this study.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study methodology's goal is to offer an organized and methodical process for choosing the best FMS by utilizing the entropy and EDAS techniques. The methodology seeks to integrate both qualitative and quantitative criteria to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of FMS alternatives. By leveraging entropy for determining objective weights, it ensures impartiality in assigning importance to each criterion, minimizing biases from subjective judgments. The primary goal is to enhance decision-making accuracy in FMS selection by addressing multiple conflicting factors, such as cost, efficiency, flexibility, and technological compatibility. Additionally, the methodology aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of the entropy-based EDAS method in real-world applications, validating its utility in complex industrial environments. This approach provides a replicable and transparent framework for decision-makers in manufacturing industries to optimize their systems and improve productivity. Ultimately, it seeks to fill the gap in existing research by applying an MCDM method to FMS selection.

3.1. The Shannon's Entropy Method

Information uncertainty is quantified using the idea of entropy. Information entropy, as defined by Isik and Adali [15], is a measure of how disordered a system is and how much valuable information can be extracted from the available data. Numerous papers have employed the weighted entropy method to resolve multi-criteria decision-making issues. Shemshadi et al. [26], for instance, employed the Entropy approach with fuzzy VIKOR for supplier selection. In another study, Zhengyuan et al. [35] combined the Entropy method and the Fuzzy Comprehensive method to evaluate

the operational capability of the regional energy grid company. Zhang et al. [33] used TOPSIS and information Entropy to evaluate tourism competitiveness. Safari et al. [25] combined PROMETHEE and Entropy methods for supplier selection. Zhao and Guo [34] made a green supplier selection for the purchase of thermal power equipment using fuzzy Entropy and fuzzy TOPSIS methods. Sun et al. [28] used TOPSIS and Entropy methods to evaluate network services. The authors Dwivedi and Sharma [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], and [12] used the entropy method in their work for calculating the criterion weight. Basuki [1] used Entropy and VIKOR methods for sustainable strategy selection for SMEs.

This method can be summarized in 5 steps according to Wang and Lee [32]; Li et al. [21]:

Step 1: As the first stage, a decision matrix (DM) containing criteria and alternatives is created. Equation 1 shows the decision matrix:

$$DM = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

In the equation (1), a_{ij} represents the performance in the criterion. This decision matrix includes a total of $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ criteria and $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ alternatives.

Step 2: The values in the decision matrix are standardized with the help of equations in equations (2) and (3). Equation (2) is used for beneficial criteria, while equation (3) is used for non-beneficial criteria. The r_{ij} values in the equations show the standardized version of the a_{ij} value.

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\max_j a_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

$$r_{ij} = \frac{\min_j a_{ij}}{a_{ij}} \quad (3)$$

Step 3: Standardized values are normalized with the help of equation 4. The s_{ij} value in equation (4) shows the normalized value.

$$s_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m r_{ij}} \quad (4)$$

Step 4: After the normalization process, the entropy value of each criterion is obtained using equation (5). The value of H_j shown in the equation below represents the entropy of the j criterion.

$$H_j = -\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n s_{ij} \log_2 s_{ij}}{\log_2 m} \quad (5)$$

Step 5: In the last step, the weight of each criterion is obtained with the help of equation (6).

$$w_j = \frac{1-H_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n 1-H_j} \quad (6)$$

The value of w_j in equation (6) represents the objective weight of the criterion. Through the application of the entropy method, these objective criterion weights are determined. After the last step of this method, the EDAS method is used and the objective weights found by this method are transferred to rank the alternatives.

3.2 The EDAS Method

The EDAS is an MCDM method used to assess and rank alternatives across various criteria. This method assesses how close or far an alternative is from an average solution, considering both positive and negative distances from the average.

This method is evaluated and selects the suppliers based on criteria such as quality, cost, and delivery time. This prioritizes projects or tasks considering factors like cost, benefit, risk, and time. Distributing resources effectively among competing projects or departments. Assessing policy options based on social, economic, and ecological criteria. Choosing the best product design considering multiple factors like cost, functionality, and customer preference.

The EDAS method is a powerful tool for decision-makers dealing with complex scenarios involving multiple criteria. Its ability to provide a balanced evaluation of alternatives, simplicity, and robustness make it a popular choice in various fields.

The EDAS technique was utilized to compute the performance of alternatives and

then rank the alternatives. The EDAS technique consists of the following steps according to Torkayesh [30], [31], and Ghorabae et al. [14]. The decision matrix developed for the entropy approach is carried over to this method.

Constructing the average solutions matrix: In this step, determining the average solutions of the matrix (AV_j) is formed by taking the average solutions of the criteria.

$$AV = [AV_j]_{1 \times m} \quad (7)$$

Where AV_j represents the average of criterion j and is calculated by the subsequent equation.

$$AV_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij}}{n} \quad (8)$$

Obtaining the distance from average: For each criterion, calculate the positive distance (PDA) as well as the negative distance (NDA) from the average by using (9) and (10), and then matrices are obtained. Based on whether the objective is benefit-based or cost-based, various equations are used to compute each element of the generated matrices (PDA_{ij} , NDA_{ij}).

$$PDA = [PDA_{ij}]_{n \times m} \quad (9)$$

$$NDA = [NDA_{ij}]_{n \times m} \quad (10)$$

The value of PDA_{ij} and NDA_{ij} represent the following equations, if j^{th} criterion is beneficial then we have

$$PDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (a_{ij} - AV_j))}{AV_j} \quad (11)$$

$$NDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (AV_j - a_{ij}))}{AV_j} \quad (12)$$

The value of PDA_{ij} and NDA_{ij} represent the following equations, if j^{th} criterion is a non-beneficial criterion then we have

$$PDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (AV_j - a_{ij}))}{AV_j} \quad (13)$$

$$NDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (a_{ij} - AV_j))}{AV_j} \quad (14)$$

Where PDA_{ij} is positive distance and NDA_{ij} is the negative distance.

Calculation of Weighted Total Positive and Negative Values: With the help of the following equations (15) and (16) are calculated the weighted positive value (WP_i) and weighted negative value (WN_i) respectively. The equation is multiplied by the weight of the criteria computed by using Shannon's entropy method, and the computation is done as follows.

$$SP_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j PDA_{ij} \quad (15)$$

$$SN_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j NDA_{ij} \quad (16)$$

Where w_j is as above. Then, with the help of the following equations, normalized obtained values (17) and (18) are calculated for all criteria.

$$NSP_i = \frac{SP_i}{\max_i(SP_i)} \quad (17)$$

$$NSN_i = 1 - \frac{SN_i}{\max_i(SN_i)} \quad (18)$$

Evaluation of Alternatives: Finally, for each alternative the appraisal scores (AS_i) are evaluated as follows.

$$AS_i = \frac{1}{2}(NSP_i + NSN_i) \quad (19)$$

Alternative appraisal score (AS_i) is ranked by decreasing value and the highest value is chosen, where $0 \leq AS_i \leq 1$ among the other alternatives as to the best choice.

4. AN APPLICATION OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

The FMS is innovative manufacturing systems that manage and create a wide range of products with minimum operator interaction. They combine automated material handling systems, centralized control systems, and computer-controlled equipment to achieve high levels of flexibility and productivity. FMS allows for the production of different models and variants of vehicles on the same production line without significant downtime or reconfiguration. It ensures components and subassemblies are produced in sync with

demand, reducing inventory costs and improving efficiency. It is capable of producing various electronic products, such as smartphones and laptops, which require frequent design changes and updates. Industries with high customization, quick adaptability, and efficient production traditionally use FMS. The particular form in which an FMS system takes is particularly useful in automotive manufacturing where multiple variants and parts have to be assembled on the same assembly line. This leads to seamless changes between design products without downtime, therefore increasing productivity and minimizing costs. FMS is used in electronics to support the rapid creation of circuit boards and components to meet evolving consumer requirements. Aerospace industries make use of FMS for manufacturing complex parts with precision; consistency and quality are assured. The FMS is important because its adaptability enables FMS to sway the dynamic market needs with the least possible actual contamination in the assets.

As industries worldwide adopt Industry 4.0 practices, research in FMS ensures that manufacturers stay competitive by leveraging the latest advancements in automation and digitalization. The FMS is enhancing the resilience of manufacturing systems to respond to global supply chain disruptions, fluctuating demands, and unforeseen challenges. In summary, FMS plays a crucial role in modern manufacturing, and ongoing research is essential to harness its full potential, ensuring adaptability, efficiency, and competitiveness in a rapidly evolving industrial landscape.

In this study, we have taken data from the literature by Rao and Parnichkun [24] for the selection problem of an FMS. They identified seven criteria with eight alternatives for the flexible manufacturing system problem. These seven criteria are as follows; reduction in labor cost (C-1), the percentage reduction in installation cost (C-2), the percentage reduction in the amount of backlog between process steps (C-3), increase in market response (C-4), increase in quality (C-5), floor area in square meters (C-6), capital and maintenance cost in thousand dollars (C-7). Of these seven criteria, the first five criteria were determined as beneficial criteria and the last two criteria were

determined as non-beneficial criteria. The data in the decision matrix of the problem is tabulated in Table 1. The optimization of the criteria is represented by (max) for the beneficial criteria and (min) for the non-beneficial criteria.

Table 1. Decision matrix for selection of the best FMS.

Alter. Opti.	C-1 max	C-2 max	C-3 max	C-4 max	C-5 max	C-6 min	C-7 min
A-1	30	5	23	0.745	0.745	5000	1500
A-2	18	15	13	0.745	0.745	6000	1300
A-3	15	10	12	0.5	0.5	7000	950
A-4	25	13	20	0.745	0.745	4000	1200
A-5	14	14	18	0.255	0.745	3500	950
A-6	17	9	15	0.745	0.5	5250	1250
A-7	23	20	18	0.5	0.745	3000	1100
A-8	16	14	8	0.255	0.5	3000	1500

The decision matrix is standardized by applying the first step of the Entropy method. Table 2 shows the standardized decision matrix. The standardized decision matrix is normalized with the help of (4). The normalized decision matrix is tabulated in Table 3.

Table 2. Standardized decision matrix for the FMS.

Alter. Opti.	C-1 max	C-2 max	C-3 max	C-4 max	C-5 max	C-6 min	C-7 min
A-1	1.00	0.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.60	0.63
A-2	0.60	0.75	0.57	1.00	1.00	0.50	0.73
A-3	0.50	0.50	0.52	0.67	0.67	0.43	1.00
A-4	0.83	0.65	0.87	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.79
A-5	0.47	0.70	0.78	0.34	1.00	0.86	1.00
A-6	0.57	0.45	0.65	1.00	0.67	0.57	0.76
A-7	0.77	1.00	0.78	0.67	1.00	1.00	0.86
A-8	0.53	0.70	0.35	0.34	0.67	1.00	0.63

The entropy of each criterion is calculated using (5), after normalization. The criterion weights are reached by performing the last step of the entropy method and it is calculated by (6). The weights of the criterion computed by the Entropy method and the weight of each criterion are tabulated in the last row of Table 3. A graphical illustration of the criterion weight is given in Figure 1.

Now, we will utilize the EDAS method, after calculating the criterion weight. In the first step, determining the average solutions of the matrix (AV_j) is formed by taking the average solutions of the criteria in the normalization process. Table 4 shows the average value that can be calculated by equation (8). An average value, or mean, is a measure of central tendency that summarizes a dataset by giving a single value

as a measure of what is typically the center of that dataset. The first one is calculated as a sum of all data values divided by the number of observations in a particular variable.

Table 3. Normalized decision matrix for the FMS.

Alter. Opti.	C-1 max	C-2 max	C-3 max	C-4 max	C-5 max	C-6 min	C-7 min
A-1	0.19	0.05	0.18	0.17	0.14	0.11	0.10
A-2	0.11	0.15	0.10	0.17	0.14	0.09	0.11
A-3	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.10	0.08	0.16
A-4	0.16	0.13	0.16	0.17	0.14	0.13	0.12
A-5	0.09	0.14	0.14	0.06	0.14	0.15	0.16
A-6	0.11	0.09	0.12	0.17	0.10	0.10	0.12
A-7	0.15	0.20	0.14	0.11	0.14	0.18	0.13
A-8	0.10	0.14	0.06	0.06	0.10	0.18	0.10
AV_j	19.75	12.5	15.88	0.56	0.65	4594	1219

The criterion weights value are as follows: 0.12, 0.21, 0.15, 0.26, 0.06, 0.15, 0.05.

Figure 1. Criterion weight score with ranking.

When the entropy value is examined, the criteria are listed as follows according to their weights; $C - 4 > C - 2 > C - 6 > C - 3 > C - 1 > C - 5 > C - 7$. The most significant criterion is selected as C-4 (market response) based on the entropy method. The entropy technique's criteria weights are transferred to the EDAS technique. The EDAS approach is used on the decision matrix displayed in Table 1. After calculating the average solution of the decision matrix, we evaluate the PDA as well as the NDA from Table 3 by using (9) and (10). Table 4 and Table 5 show the value of PDM and NDM respectively.

After calculating NDA and PDA, then multiply the normalized PDA by the corresponding criterion weight. This value represents the weighted contribution of how well an alternative performs above average. And calculated by multiplying the normalized

NDA by the corresponding criterion weight. This value represents the weighted contribution of how poorly an alternative performs below average.

Table 4. Positive decision matrix from the average value.

Alter. Opti.	C-1 max	C-2 max	C-3 max	C-4 max	C-5 max	C-6 min	C-7 min
A-1	0.52	0.00	0.45	0.33	0.14	0.00	0.00
A-2	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.33	0.14	0.00	0.00
A-3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.22
A-4	0.27	0.04	0.26	0.33	0.14	0.13	0.02
A-5	0.00	0.12	0.13	0.00	0.14	0.24	0.22
A-6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00
A-7	0.16	0.60	0.13	0.00	0.14	0.35	0.10
A-8	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.35	0.00

Finally, weighted positive values (SP_i) and weighted negative values (SN_i), weighted positive normalized value (NSP_i), weighted negative normalized value (NSN_i), and appraisal scores (AS_i) are computed. Graphical representation of SP_i, SN_i, NSP_i and NSN_i shown in Figure 2. The final ranking of flexible manufacturing systems is shown in Table 6 and Figure 3 illustrates the flexible manufacturing systems and their final ranking based on Entropy and EADS techniques.

Table 5. Negative decision matrix from the average value.

Alter. Opti.	C-1 max	C-2 max	C-3 max	C-4 max	C-5 max	C-6 min	C-7 min
A-1	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.23
A-2	0.09	0.00	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.07
A-3	0.24	0.20	0.24	0.11	0.23	0.52	0.00
A-4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
A-5	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.55	0.00	0.00	0.00
A-6	0.14	0.28	0.06	0.00	0.23	0.14	0.03
A-7	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.00
A-8	0.19	0.00	0.50	0.55	0.23	0.00	0.23

Table 6. Final ranking of the FMS by the EDAS method.

Alter.	SP_i	SN_i	NSP_i	NSN_i	AS_i	Rank
A-1	0.22	0.15	0.95	0.42	0.68	3
A-2	0.13	0.09	0.58	0.67	0.62	4
A-3	0.01	0.23	0.05	0.13	0.09	8
A-4	0.19	0.00	0.82	1.00	0.91	2
A-5	0.10	0.17	0.43	0.33	0.38	6
A-6	0.08	0.12	0.36	0.54	0.45	5
A-7	0.23	0.03	1.00	0.89	0.95	1
A-8	0.08	0.26	0.33	0.00	0.17	7

Figure 2. Graphical representation of SP_i, SN_i, NSP_i , and NSN_i .

Figure 3. Illustration of FMS ranking with the score.

Based on the evaluation results from the EDAS approach, it is seen that the best FMS is A-7 followed by A-4, A-1, A-2, A-6, A-5, A-8, and A-3.

The FMS identified as A-7 is the best option for the particular application of the industrial work under the current parameters, according to the FMS findings above; A-4 is the second choice. These outcomes are similar to those proposed by Rao & Parnichkun [24] with the fuzzy programming technique for multiple objectives. It should be noted, nevertheless, that the user's assessments of relative relevance determine the ranking. If the user gives the characteristics varying relative priority values, the ranking that is shown could alter. The method put forward by Karsak and Kuzgunkaya [18] is equivalent in this regard. The underlying concept is that criteria with higher variability (or more "entropy") contain more information and should be given more weight. In contrast, the approach presented in this work offers a clear-cut, rational, and basic process for solving the FMS selection problem.

5. DISCUSSION

Worldwide manufacturing rivalry has compelled businesses to think about cutting

costs while boosting quality and customization response. The development of FMSs promises enormous possibilities for enhancing flexibility and altering the competitive landscape by simultaneously guaranteeing cost-effectiveness and customized manufacture. Before investing in such innovative manufacturing methods that demand large capital outlays, one must take into account both the impacts that are easily quantified in dollars and those that are not. While precision-based approaches have been previously suggested to tackle the assessment and choice of flexible manufacturing technologies, these approaches are complex, knowledge-intensive, and maybe beyond the reach of the individual decision-maker or user organization. A straightforward and rational scientific approach or mathematical instrument is required to assist user organizations in making an appropriate decision. This work proposes a methodology for choosing an appropriate FMS from a wide range of alternative FMSs. The methodology is based on a combinatorial mathematical approach combined with Shannon's entropy. When compared to other approaches that have been suggested in the past for choosing an FMS, this strategy is easier to put into practice.

The flexible manufacturing systems selection characteristics function created in this work aids in the creation of the flexible manufacturing systems selection index, which assesses and ranks flexible manufacturing systems for a particular selection problem and may concurrently take into account any number of both quantitative and qualitative FMS selection attributes. In addition, the article proposes an entropy and EDAS conversion scale with ranked value judgments to express the qualitative FMS selection feature.

The suggested technique is unique in that it provides a generic process that may be used for a variety of management science selection challenges that involve ambiguity and several both qualitative and quantitative selection qualities. Practical issues could come up when this kind of technique is put into practice.

It is necessary to ascertain the values corresponding to the qualities of several possible FMS that the suggested technique would assess. These figures might occasionally be estimates. A what-if study including many

runs of the suggested model can be necessary due to a lack of precise and trustworthy data. What-if analysis may benefit from further methodological advancements for more effective execution.

6. CONCLUSION

The production systems are very important systems for producing the same types of products in the same quantity. Many manufacturing firms adopt flexible production systems to take advantage of the benefits provided by FMS. Many criteria are taken into account when selecting or evaluating any production system. Also, these criteria are sometimes confused with bias. Therefore, it is appropriate to use MCDM methods in FMS selection and evaluation. In this study, the Entropy-based EDAS method is proposed for FMS selection. The entropy method is used to find the weights of the objective criteria that are used in FMS selection. The EDAS method ranks these systems according to the performance they show in the criteria of flexible production systems. Selecting an FMS is a complex decision involving multiple factors. The main problems encountered in this process include:

- Capital Expenditure: The initial setup of an FMS requires substantial investment in advanced machinery, automation, and software systems.
- Cost Justification: Justifying the high upfront costs with anticipated long-term benefits and returns on investment can be challenging.
- Compatibility: Ensuring the new FMS integrates seamlessly with existing systems and processes, such as ERP and supply chain management systems, is complex.
- Customization: Adapting the FMS to specific production requirements and workflow can be difficult and time-consuming.
- Rapid Technological Changes: Keeping up with rapid advancements in manufacturing technology, automation, and software can make the selection process difficult.
- Obsolescence: The risk of investing in technology that may become obsolete quickly due to continuous technological innovation.

- Future Needs: Predicting future production needs and ensuring the selected FMS can scale and adapt to these changing requirements is problematic.
- Versatility: Ensuring the system can handle a wide variety of products and production volumes without significant reconfiguration.
- Workforce Training: Implementing an FMS requires a skilled workforce capable of operating and maintaining sophisticated machinery and software.
- Change Management: Managing the transition and training employees to adapt to new processes and technologies.
- Downtime: Ensuring the reliability and minimal downtime of an FMS is critical, as any failure can lead to significant production losses.
- Maintenance Costs: Ongoing maintenance and potential repairs can be costly and require specialized skills.
- By carefully considering these factors and adopting a strategic approach, companies can mitigate the challenges associated with selecting and implementing Flexible Manufacturing Systems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Several suggestions may be made to improve decision-making and guarantee ideal results based on the examination of choosing FMS utilizing the EDAS and Entropy methods. By using an impartial approach to weight assignment based on data variability, the entropy technique makes sure that more important criteria receive the proper attention. The Entropy technique makes sure that the decision-making process is grounded in real data by examining the inherent unpredictability in the criteria, producing more accurate and dependable results. By combining these approaches, one may make decisions that are more informed and more balanced by ensuring that the criterion weights are established fairly and that the alternatives are thoroughly evaluated. By eliminating prejudices and guaranteeing a comprehensive assessment of every option, this integrated method improves the selection process's accuracy. Decide which important factors—such as cost, maintenance needs, flexibility, scalability, and technology compatibility—are essential to the FMS's

performance and adaptability. Organizations may greatly improve their process for choosing Flexible Manufacturing Systems by combining the EDAS approach for comprehensive option evaluation with the Entropy method for objective weight determination. These suggestions guarantee a thorough, data-driven, and well-rounded approach, which will finally result in the selection of a more strategic and successful FMS.

The integration of the Entropy and EDAS MCDM methods offers several advantages for future applications and research, enhancing the robustness, objectivity, and effectiveness of decision-making processes in various fields. The Entropy and EDAS MCDM methods are valuable tools for future research and applications, providing objective, balanced, and comprehensive decision-making frameworks. Their adaptability, versatility, and rigorous approach make them well-suited for addressing complex, multi-faceted problems across various domains. By incorporating these methods, researchers can enhance the quality, relevance, and impact of their work, paving the way for more informed and effective decision-making in the future.

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NDA

Negative distance from
average

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NOMENCLATURE

EDAS	Evaluation based on the Distance from Average Solution
MCDM	Multi-criteria Decision Making
FMS	flexible manufacturing systems
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
EVAMIX	Evaluation of Mixed Data Complex Proportional Assessment
COPRAS	Organization, Rangement Et Synthese De Donnes Relationnelles
OCRA	Operational Competitiveness Rating
DEMATAL	Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory CRiteria Importance
CRITIC	Through Inter-criteria Correlation
PROMETHEE	Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation
ELECTRE	Elimination and Choice Translating Reality
ROV	Range of value
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
VIKOR	VIekriterijumsko KOMpromisno Rangiranje
PDA	Positive distance from average